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Internal Communication In Family Microenterprises In Times Of Pandemic

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109

Abstract

The following research aims to analyze the importance of internal communication in family microenterprises in times of pandemic, alluding to the one generated by COVID-19. The methodology used is non-experimental and with a qualitative approach. Different sources of information, books, articles, magazines and videos were consulted, highlighting different points of view of authors in order to carry out a documentary type research, in addition an analysis of each of the sources consulted was carried out and it was obtained as a result that internal communication in microenterprises is fundamental because it allows the members to know their responsibilities in order to carry them out effectively, This is especially true when there are challenges such as working during a pandemic, learning to communicate in a good way without losing the reason for the existence of the community they are part of.

Keywords: Microenterprises, Internal Communication, Pandemic, Family.

Introduction

Microenterprises are all those businesses that have fewer than 10 workers, generate annual sales of up to 4 million pesos and represent 95 per cent of all enterprises and 40 per cent of employment in the country; in addition, they produce 15 percent of the Gross Domestic Product. (Secretary of Economy, 2010).

On the other hand, the set of activities carried out by an organization for the creation and maintenance of good relations with and among its members through the use of different means of communication that keeps them informed, integrated and motivated so that they contribute with their work to the achievement of organizational objectives, is called internal communication (Torres L. 2012, as cited in Oyarvide-Ramírez, Reyes-Sarria, Montaña-Colorado. 2017, p. 229).

According to (Bermúdez, n.d., p.6) Communication refers to a process of interaction by which people exchange information: it is the correspondence between two or more people and the transmission of signals through a common code between emitters, receivers and vice versa. This communication is transferred to the organizations where it becomes a transversal element in which each of the members participate and intertwine.

It is necessary to maintain good communication in micro businesses because it offers them the advantage of being able to share activities or tasks among the members of this same, publicize how to carry them out, as well as participate together and work harmoniously.

This is how internal communication becomes relevant by virtue of the global crisis of CORONAVIRUS-19 that is currently being experienced, as both small and large companies have chosen to look for actions to survive without losing it, adapting to the new way of working from home, in the same way using new tools, especially giving rise to technology, which is undoubtedly becoming more innovative.

From one day to the next, the routine of working and living together more than eight hours a day was broken. And there was internal communication, at a critical and unimaginable moment at the beginning of this convulsive 2020, demonstrating that its function far exceeds the mere informative work to workers and / or collaborators. Its function as a catalyst for teams, facilitating coordination and generating commitment, has been fundamental in this kind of war against an invisible enemy that we still do not fully know (Navarro, 2020).

Methodology

This article used a documentary methodology when conducting research with validated information and in relation to the research topic. Similarly, we opted for the use of information obtained from different sources such as published articles, documents and videos of formal information to carry out a theoretical analysis of the subject of study.

The types of studies carried out are exploratory and analytical, since topics related to internal communication in family microenterprises, importance of effective communication in business and communication in times of pandemic were investigated and analyzed.

The realization of this article is based on the importance of internal communication in times of pandemic in microenterprises and how they have managed to maintain it during the crisis, therefore, when carrying out this study ways to maintain themselves as a company are known, since these businesses occupy a great place for the economy of the country helping in the economic progress of families.

Regarding the analysis of the data obtained in the present studies, studies carried out previously will be used, reviewing related theories and real and documented situations.

In this context, this research, as well as the discussion presented in it, is of interest to microentrepreneur families who have not yet used good communication or who do not give the importance that internal communication occupies for their businesses, in addition to joining the public interested in this topic.

Development.

Internal communication

Communication could be technically defined as a process through which a set of meanings takes the form of a message and is transferred to a person or a group of them, in such a way that the perceived meaning must be equivalent to what the initiators of it tried to convey (Luke, 1997 as cited in Charry, 2008).

For his part, Millar defines it as "that behavioral situation in which a source transmits a message to a receiver with the conscious intention of affecting his subsequent behavior" (Arizcuren, Cabezas, Cañeque, Casado, Fernández, Lacasta, Martín, Menchaca, Núñez, Sánchez, Soria, Vicario, 2008).

Thus, the main function that internal communication develops in the institution is to support the business project through a coherent and planned communication management, regardless of the mission of the organization. In addition, it allows to publicize the objectives and policies of the organization and to form its own identity based on a climate of motivation and cordiality (Graverán, 2017 as cited in Oyarvide-Ramírez, et al. 2017, p. 301).

Thus, when internal communication is aligned with the general strategy of the institution, it must meet the following objectives:

- Integrate all workers to the objectives, norms, policies and goals of the organization, achieving the motivation of workers and increasing the sense of belonging to the organization.
- Establish a positive social and psychological climate in the organization, communicating openly to managers and workers and promoting positive values in the workforce.
- Encourage the participation of workers in the various tasks that are oriented to the realization of institutional objectives.
- Favor the creation of a positive image in both the internal and external public that is consistent with their institutional identity and that leads to optimal organizational results (Grillo G., 2007 as cited in Oyarvide-Ramírez, et al. 2017, p. 301).

When analyzing each of the concepts of internal communication, it can be mentioned that one of the characteristics of this, highlights that through it essential activities are carried out for business and above all that make it work, through good communication, employees establish relationships to communicate with each other and guide them towards the achievement of organizational objectives.

Internal communication in times of pandemic (COVID-19)

After the Covid-19 pandemic, in the reports, evaluations and internal reports of organizations, the sections dedicated to internal communication will have to start writing in bold and underlined. And it is that at this point there should be few who question the usefulness of this tool, of enormous strategic value for management. Its effects on workers during this unprecedented period of confinement and teleworking have been tremendously positive, supporting businesses in building a remote "community" and uniting teams at a time clearly conditioned by the absence of physical contact and direct interaction of employees.

Technology and digitalization – there is no doubt – have also been great allies to achieve this (Navarro, 2020).

Para (Godoy & Opazo, 2021) The pandemic has forced companies to develop online remote work systems at full speed. Teleworking suddenly became a widespread practice. Organizations thus became pure (digital) communication.

Since the appearance of COVID-19, companies must question the decision and implementation of actions in the short term in the flow of internal communication to fulfill institutional purposes, giving added value to their corporate identity; Therefore, this implies that the activities carried out must respond to a much greater objective than the needs of the context: maintaining active corporate values and employee cohesion. (Avilés, 2020).

As we have seen, internal communication and especially in times of crisis forces companies to take different alternatives to fulfill their purposes and to achieve this, technology has been indispensable, giving as an opportunity to be in virtual contact with co-workers, continue with activities without being stopped, although with modifications in the way of carrying them out.

In addition to knowing how to maintain good communication and achieve a united work team, new work strategies are also obtained for future crises, knowing what to do later prepares the organization and especially the employees so that they do not feel lost and that they are really effective, because unfortunately after the COVID-19 pandemic, Many businesses disappeared and others have managed to survive, others opened doors.

According to the National Institute of Statistics and Geography (INEGI), 2020 presents the second set of results of the Study on Business Demography (EDN) 2020 and it is estimated that:

As reported in 2020 with the first set of results, of the 4.9 million micro, small and medium establishments reported by the 2019 Economic Censuses, the EDN 2020 estimates that 3.9 million (79.2%) survived 17 months after the census survey ended.

In the same period, it is estimated that 1,010,857 establishments, representing 20.8%, closed their doors definitively, and 619,443 establishments were born, representing 12.8% of the country's business population.

When comparing the total number of economic units estimated by the EDN in September 2020 with those captured by the Economic Censuses in May 2019, there is a decrease of 8.1 percent.

On the other hand, according to (United Nations, n.d.) declares that the COVID-19 pandemic is having a very profound impact on the economy and society of Latin America and the Caribbean. ECLAC estimates that 2.7 million companies could close before the end of 2020, equivalent to 19% of all firms in the region. In the case of microenterprises, this percentage could reach 21%.

In terms of employment, this would lead to the destruction of more than 8.5 million jobs: 8.1% of total formal employment in the business sector and more than a fifth of the jobs generated by microenterprises (see figure 1).

Figure 1

Latin America and the Caribbean (27 countries): percentage of companies that could close and jobs lost, by company size.

As you can see, the pandemic has left great consequences, the loss of jobs mostly, is a factor that affects especially the economy of our country, some microenterprises came to failure, but others were able to maintain.

Conclusions

The current pandemic has brought a variety of changes in all aspects, has forced the entire population to adapt to new ways of living and above all working, change from coexistence to isolation and therefore to maintain communication despite this.

As seen in this article, internal communication does not refer only to delegating tasks and giving instructions to employees, rather it refers to knowing how to communicate the actions to be performed, but making them participate in them as part of the same team.

The workers and other internal people of the microenterprises are very important and indispensable elements because it is through them how the company works, this is how internal communication takes a fundamental role since it represents the functions that guide towards the achievement of business objectives and goals.

It is important to bear in mind that internal communication and especially when it is effective directs the employees of the company so that they know their responsibilities and how to perform them, thanks to it the company will motivate its members obtaining a good work team, informed of what happens in their workplace, In this way they provide opinions and seek solutions to problems, in addition to providing security and integrity in the business.

As mentioned, family microenterprises usually have problems when communicating for family reasons, however, in order to grow as a company it is necessary to commit yourself, take into account family and business issues, do not confuse them and much less combine them, in this way you can find solutions to each problem that arises where all members agree and work together.

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